

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PROJECT- BASED INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING STUDENTS IN THE SPHERE OF TAX AND TAXATION!

Bobokeldieva Maftuna Abdusamad qizi

Fiscal Institute, teacher

bobokeldievamaftuna0@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588190>

Abstract: This article provides a brief overview of the role of project-based learning and the international experience of corporate taxation, as well as the tax reforms of our republic.

Key words: tax, budget, economy, export.

In order to intensify the educational process at the Institute of Economics and Business, the Department of Economic Security, Accounting and Audit has been introducing project-based learning since 2017.

Project activity is an important part of the educational activity of students in project-oriented BEP, the main purpose of which is the independent acquisition of knowledge in the process of solving theoretical and practical problems or problems that require the integration of knowledge from various subject areas of science.

Project-based learning, in our opinion, is a self-managed activity of students aimed at developing the competencies of students in the process of creating a specific project with the presentation of results. The participation of students in project activities makes it possible to reduce the gap between theory and practice during training [1].

Solving the problem in the implementation of project activities involves the use of a combination of various methods (research, search, problematic), the ability to apply knowledge from various fields of science, technology, and creative fields.

The basic principle of project-based learning is to establish a direct connection between educational material and practice.

students' physical experience in their cognitive and creative joint activities.

Project activity allows:

- to make the learning process as close as possible to practical activities;
- increase motivation for learning;
- change the position of students in the educational process to the maximum subjective;
- individualize the learning process and make it more intense;
- to accumulate experience for students to be included in independent professional activities;

- create conditions for the formation of general cultural and professional competencies of students.

The objectives of the project are:

- students mastering the elements of project activities in relation to solving their professional problems;

- regulation of the process of mastering general cultural, general professional and professional competencies by students of the specialty "Economic Security";

- the formation of students' professional knowledge, skills and abilities for making rational economic decisions in the design and economic and accounting and economic, information and

analytical, export

consulting, control

auditing and organizational and managerial activities of an economic entity;

- development of the economic way of thinking of a student of the specialty "Economic security", his ability to personal self-determination and self-realization;

- growth in the number of professionally oriented and motivated students;

- development of a package of methodological documents for the implementation of educational end-to-end design technology "for students

- formation of interaction between an educational institution and employers in the implementation of the project for the introduction of educational end-to-end design technology" for students of the specialty "Economic security" [1].

Results. The department attracts students to project activities starting from the third year. At the beginning of the academic year, an organizational meeting is held with students, at which they are introduced to the purpose of the project activity, the topics of scientific research, in the development of which they can participate in the course of work on the project. Students confirm their consent to participate in the project by a statement in which they indicate the chosen topic of the project. Usually 40-50% of students agree to participate in the project. At the same time, a schedule for the implementation of the relevant sections of the project activity is developed with the students. In the future, all coursework provided for by the curriculum, students perform within the framework of the chosen topic of end-to-end design in accordance with the established schedule. If additional information is needed to disclose certain aspects of the project, students write abstracts.

To help students at the department, guidelines have been developed for the implementation of end-to-end design, which give the subject of project activities carried out within the department, and detailed tasks for the disclosure of each topic. For example, a student chose the topic of the project “Ensuring the economic security of economic entities”, respectively, in the 5th semester he develops the topic - the organization of information security of the accounting system at the enterprise, in 6 - accounting and analytical support for the economic security of an economic entity, in 7 - the main directions of economic security of an economic entity subject, in 8 - the development of a project to improve the economic security of an economic entity, in 9 - tax policy as a component of the effectiveness of the economic security system of an economic entity, in 10 - an internal control system as an element of ensuring the economic security of an economic entity, and in the same semester writes an essay on the topic - diagnostics of the economic security of an economic entity [2].

As a result, students approach the defense of final qualification works professionally prepared, having studied the activities of a particular business entity in all aspects, namely, from the point of view of ensuring economic security, organizing internal control, taxation, organizing financial and management accounting, etc.

Each teacher leads several projects. Teachers of the department have completed advanced training courses on the organization of project activities.

When carrying out project activities, we strive to develop students' creative activity, and not follow the direct instructions of the project leaders. We believe that participation in project activities enhances students' motivation for learning, improves academic performance, develops creative initiative, and also forms a student's personal portfolio for further successful employment.

Students report the results of project activities at the scientific practical conferences, published in the press. As the end result of the project study, there may be proposals aimed at the financial recovery of business entities, optimization of taxation, improvement of financial, tax and management accounting, and others. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the project takes place in each semester by protecting the results of a specific study in accordance with the schedule for the implementation of project activities [2].

An important role in the interest of students in participating in project activities, as practice has shown, is played by the formulation of topics by the teachers of

the department. If the topic is irrelevant, has a weak potential, then the work is done at a low level.

The department aims students at project activities and during the period of training practices. For this, before

a meeting at which students are divided into groups of 5-7 people and each group is given a task with detailed content. At the end of the practice, students defend their projects at a meeting of the department.

Conclusion. The practice of introducing project-based learning is new for us and therefore we are constantly improving it. So in the next academic year, we plan to offer a group of students of 5 people each semester one topic of the project in order to reveal and resolve it in different ways and techniques. This will provide an opportunity to develop the creative component of the project and implement the participants' own decisions.

Thus, we believe that in the course of project activities, students acquire teamwork skills, the need to comply with established project delivery schedules, and the experience of public presentation of research results.

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